

IMPACT OF TV ADVERTISEMENT ON VIEWERS BUYING BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract:

Advertising is nothing more than the use of bright ideas, stunts and slogans to popularize goods, which appeal to the great body or ordinary consumers.. The study aims To determine the impact of TV advertisement on viewers buying behaviour in Pollachi Taluk.. The study was based on questionnaire with a sample of 100 respondents. The findings of the study are analyzed using simple percentage analysis and friedman ranking test. The study also concludes that that most of the TV viewers are attracted towards food products.

Key Words: Impact, Television, Viewers, Advertisement, World, Attract & Etc.,

Introduction:

In recent days, due to heavy competition, the manufacturers find it difficult to sell their products. In addition to the competition, the behavior of the consumer towards the products is changing at a rapid speed and also they are changing their interest towards products from one brand to another. The socio-economic setup also influences the consumer in different angles. Above all, the contents of the product, promotional method adopted by the company, and the cultural base also influence the preference of a consumer. So a company in order to increase sales and attracts more customers, adopt various promotional measures. One of such measure is advertising which is the lifeblood of every organization today.

The Ethical Aspect of Advertising:

Many of the ethical aspects of advertising border on and interact with both the social and legal, consideration of the advertising process. The ethical aspect of advertising mainly falls in three areas:

- ✓ Truth in Advertising: Avoid the false or misleading statements in an advertisement.
- ✓ Advertising to Children: Children are inexperienced consumers and an easy impact of advertisement for the sophisticated persuasiveness of advertisers. Advertising influences children's demands for everything from toys to snack foods. So, the advertisement should not create a child parent environment.
- ✓ Advertising Controversial Product: The issue of advertising controversial products like tobacco, alcoholic beverages, gambling and lotteries etc are more complex. While making advertisement for these products, it should not persuade the consumers for too much of their consumption.

Television:

Television is often called "The King" of the advertising media, since a majority of people spends more hours in watching TV per day than spending time with any other medium. It combines the use of sight, color, sound and motion. TV has proved its persuasive power in influencing human behavior from time to time. It is popular than other media because of its creativity and impact, coverage and cost effectiveness, capacity and attention, selectivity and flexibility. The interaction of sight and sound offers tremendous creative flexibility and makes dramatic life-like representation of products possible. TV commercials can be used to convey a mood or image for a brand as well as to develop emotional or entertaining appeals that help to make dull products appear interesting.

Need of the Study:

- ✓ To know the present scenario of the customer's buying behaviour.
- ✓ To know the impact of TV advertisement on customer's buying behaviour.

Reviews of Literature:

Joshi, P (2005) in his article "Increasing need to understand the changing consumer" suggested that for sports channels, product categories are different as sports-events offer a huge audience but to impress fans, advertising needs to be innovative yet appropriate. Advertisers need to focus on space more and when they do, they need to think more creatively about execution Hedges (2004). It is not easy being an FMCG marketer today. Since growth has gone down, competition has gone up, and price wars keep breaking –out, consumers are turning their attention to other product categories. There is a sense of worry amongst FMCG companies with the increasing competitions of other channel partners.

Ashwini Sovani (2008) in her article, "Cadbury's Advertisement, Yummy, Creamy and Chocolatey" stated that world over; chocolate is one product that gets almost uniform recognition. This is the product which

is normally targeted at the younger age groups across the world. Chocolates are generally used for celebration; they signify sharing of joy and happiness. It is a perfect gift for all, irrespective of the age they belong to. The television commercials are all the more appealing since the picturization of a situation connects the customers directly. Though chocolates do not find space for themselves in the Indian sweets category, Cadbury with its innovative positioning through focused commercials has been able to draw attention from the Indian customers. The advertisements are oriented towards Indian culture and ethnicity to grab the attention. This has enabled the company to make a silent entry into the Indian sweets category. The article analyzes the innovative advertisements of Cadbury chocolates.

Mrudhula G. P (2009) in her article “Advertising in Social Media”, “An Era of consumer Generated Media” stated that advertising has undergone a dramatic change. Social media have already begin make their presence felt in the recent years. It is expected that their usage will reach its peak in the coming years. Any form of advertising, either traditional or modern, requires customer’s attention in order to educate them about the products or services and finally motivate them to make the buying-decision. Social media, the new internet enabled network is delivering the holy grail to advertisers. This new solution of using social media is being increasingly used by the advertisers. This new medium provides the marketers the unique combination of reach, relevance and establishing relationships.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To determine the impact of TV advertisement on viewers buying behaviour in Pollachi Taluk.

Limitations:

- ✓ The result of the study is based upon the views expressed by the viewers of Pollachi Taluk.
- ✓ The statistical tools used to analyse the data have their own limitations.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

Area of the Study: The research study was done in Pollachi Taluk.

Nature and Source of Data: The study is based on questionnaire method; primary data has been collected from various viewers in Pollachi Taluk and the secondary data have been collected from related journals, Magazines and textbooks.

Statistical Tools Used for the Study:

- ✓ Simple Percentage Analysis
- ✓ Friedman’s Ranking Test

Sampling Used: 100 viewers were selected by convenience sampling method.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic profile of the Viewers

Factors	No of Viewers n = 100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	40	40
Female	60	60
Educational Qualification		
Up to SSLC	26	26
HSC	30	30
Above UG Degree	44	44
Monthly Income		
Up to Rs. 10000	42	42
Above Rs.10000	58	58
Type of Family		
Joint Family	58	58
Nuclear family	42	42

Inference: Table No.1 describes the demographic profile of TV Viewers towards impact on TV advertisement. Out of 100 viewers who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (60%) of the viewers are female, (44%) whose age group is under 26 to 50, most (44%) of the viewers are graduates, the monthly income of (58%) viewers is above Rs.10, 000 and (58%) viewers belong to joint family.

Table 2: Impact of TV advertisement on Customers buying behaviour

Source	Number of Viewers	Percentage
Low	38	38
Medium	50	50
High	12	12
Total	100	100

Inference: The above table shows that, out of 100 viewers, impact of TV advertisement is found to be low with regard to 38% viewers, in case of 50% viewer's impact of TV advertisement is medium and 12% viewers are highly attracted towards TV advertisement.

Table 5: Impact of TV advertisement on viewers buying behaviour– Friedman Rank Test

Factors	Average Rank	Rank
Clothes	3.7	4
Accessories	2.8	5
Food Products	6.8	1
Mobiles	5.2	3
Beverages	4.6	2
Programs	1.2	6

The above table shows about the Friedman Rank Test for policyholder's satisfaction were the level of significance is at 0.000 which shows that there is a relationship between the ranks given. The impact of TV advertisement through Friedman rank test, it is found that majority of the viewers are impacted towards food products, beverages, mobiles, clothes, accessories and Programs. Thus, it found from the above table that most of the viewers are attracted towards food products.

Conclusion:

Today, in India, there are as many as 1000 television channels with nearly millions of viewers. The consumers have diverse tastes and preferences which problem for the marketers. In the face of these difficulties, using TV advertisements has become a fashion statement for every company nowadays. Usually television has more impact on the minds of customers because advertisement through television reaches easily with audio and video. Viewers have more advertisement recalling ability. Once findings are taken into consideration with a sharper focus on good business ethics in advertisement that in turn benefit both traders and consumers.

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